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Investigations on Reactions of Molybdenum(v) Complexes in Presence of 2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzimidazole in Aqueous and Non-aqueous Media

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STABILITY, structure and bonding in the 'oxometal ions' species are greatly influenced by anionic environment and the nature of the donor atoms of the other ligands¹⁻⁴. In the present communication, we describe the isolation and characterisation of some oxomolybdate(v) bromo complexes with 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (Pybmz).

Experimental

The ligand (Pybmz) was prepared according to the literature procedure⁵. All the other reagents were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of complexes :

2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzimidazolinoxopentabromomolybdate(v), $\text{PybmzH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$: Molybdenum trioxide (~0.9 g) was reduced with boiling 48%

hydrobromic acid and to it Pybmz (0.6 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of the same acid was added with stirring. A yellow crystalline complex separated on cooling the mixture to room temperature. The solid was filtered, washed with 48% hydrobromic acid and dried under reduced pressure over solid KOH.

Oxotribromo[2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole]molybdenum(v), $[\text{MoOBr}_3\text{Pybmz}]$: PybmzH₂[MoOBr₃] (~0.6 g) was refluxed with dry ethanol (10 ml) for 1 h. The resulting brick-red crystalline solid was filtered and dried under reduced pressure.

A yellow crystalline compound of the same composition was obtained by refluxing PybmzH₂[MoOBr₃] (0.6 g) with acetonitrile (15 ml) for 2 h. The product was filtered, washed with acetonitrile and dried under reduced pressure.

Oxo-μ-oxotetrabromo[2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole]molybdenum(v), $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_4(\text{Pybmz})_2]$: A mixture of ammonium oxopentabromomolybdate (1.0 g) and dry ethanol (20 ml) was stirred for 10 min and filtered. An ethanolic solution of Pybmz (0.6 g) was then added to the filtrate. The resulting pink solid was filtered, washed with dry ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Oxo-μ-dioxobromo[2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole]molybdenum(v), $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2(\text{Pybmz})_2]$: PybmzH₂[MoOBr₃] (~0.8 g) was gently boiled with water (10 ml) for 15 min. The resulting brick-red solid was filtered, washed with cold water and dried under reduced pressure over solid KOH.

Molybdenum was estimated gravimetrically as molybdenum trioxide⁶, bromide as silver bromide⁷, and nitrogen estimated by Dumas' method. The oxidation number of molybdenum was determined by titration with ceric sulphate⁸. Room temperature (30 ± 2°) magnetic moments values were determined by Gouy method. The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra (in 9 M HBr, ethanol and acetonitrile) were recorded with a Varian 634 spectrophotometer. The results are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The conductance data of PybmzH₂[MoOBr] in aqueous medium indicate extensive hydrolysis and

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Oxidation number (z)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Λ_M Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
	Mo	Br	N			
PybmzH ₂ [MoOBr ₃]	13.63 (13.54)	56.59 (56.39)	6.04 (5.92)	5.12	1.86	—
[MoOBr ₃ Pybmz] brick-red	18.02 (17.89)	44.03 (43.84)	8.03 (7.68)	5.09	1.53	18.47
[MoOBr ₃ Pybmz] yellow	18.47 (17.89)	43.79 (43.84)	8.00 (7.68)	4.93	1.54	15.68
[Mo ₂ O ₃ Br ₄ (Pybmz) ₂]	20.45 (20.12)	33.65 (33.52)	9.20 (8.80)	4.81	1.25	18.00
[Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₂ (Pybmz) ₂]	26.32 (26.29)	21.92 (21.89)	11.72 (11.51)	4.97	Diamag.	10.94

ionisation. However, the non-electrolytic nature of $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_4(\text{Pybmz})_2]$, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2(\text{Pybmz})_2]$ and both the varieties of $[\text{MoOBr}_3\text{Pybmz}]$ was established from molar conductance data (Table 1) in dimethylsulphoxide⁹. The μ_{eff} values are in fair agreement with d^1 configuration of molybdenum(v). The hydrolytic product $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2(\text{Pybmz})_2]$ is diamagnetic due to oxo-bridging¹⁰ with the possible Mo-Mo interaction. The terminal $\nu_{\text{Mo}=\text{O}}$ band¹⁰ at 975 cm^{-1} in $\text{PybmzH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_3]$ shifted to 955 cm^{-1} in the hydrolytic product $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2(\text{Pybmz})_2]$. Such lowering of $\nu_{\text{Mo}=\text{O}}$ can be attributed to the replacement of bromide by oxygen¹¹. Electronic spectra of the salt $\text{PybmzH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_3]$ in 9 M HBr show two bands at $14\ 500$ and $22\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(\text{I})$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$, and four charge transfer bands at $24\ 200$, $25\ 800$, $30\ 000$ and $41\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(\text{II})$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(\text{I})$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(\text{II})$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(\text{III})$, respectively. For the remaining complexes the electronic spectral bands appeared around $13\ 800$, $22\ 000$, $25\ 000$, $31\ 000$ and $42\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(\text{I})$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$, $L \rightarrow \text{Mo}$ charge transfer, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(\text{I})$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(\text{II})$ transitions, respectively.

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Complexes of 2,4-Dimercapto-*s*-triazolo[4,3-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole with some Platinum Metal Ions. Part-II

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IN an early communication¹, the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} with 2,4-dimercapto-*s*-triazolo[4,3-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole (abbreviated as DTTH_2) have been reported. Now we report the complexes of Pd^{II} , Pt^{II} , Ru^{II} and Rh^{III} with DTTH_2 . Previously it was shown¹ that DTTH_2 coordinates

either as a monobasic or a dibasic acidic molecule in basic medium. Now we have found that DTTH_2 can coordinate as a neutral sulphur donor as well with platinum metal ions (Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}) in acidic solution ($\text{pH} \approx 1-2$).

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by the reported method². The metal salts used were of Johnson Mathey.

Preparation of metal complexes :

$M(\text{DTTH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2$ ($M = \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$ or Pt^{II}) : An ethanolic solution ($\text{pH} \approx 1-2$) of the metal chloride (0.001 mol in 20 ml) and hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.002 mol in 30 ml) were mixed with stirring when dichloro complexes separated immediately. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in an air-oven at $50-60^\circ$.

$M(\text{DTTH})_2$ ($M = \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$, Pt^{II} or Ru^{II}) and $\text{Rh}(\text{DTTH})_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Ethanolic solutions of the metal (Pd^{II} , Pt^{II} or Ru^{II}) chloride or rhodium(III) chloride (0.001 mol in 30 ml) and the ligand in stoichiometric ratio were mixed and refluxed on a steam-bath for ~ 1 h, when the complex separated gradually. It was filtered, washed and dried as above.

$\text{Ru}(\text{DTT})\text{Py} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: An aqueous ethanolic solution of ruthenium(II) chloride (0.002 mol in 30 ml) and the ligand (0.002 mol in 30 ml) were mixed and refluxed with pyridine (5 ml) on a steam-bath for 0.5 h when a dark green precipitate separated out gradually. The product was filtered, washed and dried as above.

$M(\text{DTT})\text{Py}_2$ ($M = \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$ or Pt^{II}) and $\text{Rh}_2(\text{DTT})_2 \cdot \text{Py}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: An aqueous ethanolic solution of the metal chloride (0.002 mol in 30 ml) was made alkaline by adding excess pyridine and refluxed with the ligand dissolved in ethanol-pyridine mixture in stoichiometric proportion ($\text{pH} = 7-8$) when red or yellow complex separated out immediately. The precipitate was digested on a steam-bath, filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over KOH in an atmosphere of pyridine.

The colour and analytical results of the complexes are shown in Table 1. Ir spectra of the complexes were recorded³ in the range $4\ 000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The solid reflectance spectra were recorded on a Beckman DU 500 spectrophotometer in the range $220-850\text{ nm}$ taking MgCO_3 as the standard.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are almost insoluble in water as well as in the usual organic solvents; however, the complexes $M(\text{DTTH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $M(\text{DTTH})_2$ are slightly soluble in DMF. The hydrated complexes retain water molecules below $90-100^\circ$ indicating that they are strongly held up in crystal lattices or bonded to the metal atom. The pyridine adducts are also stable in air and do not lose pyridine below